

IMPROVING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION FIELD

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ABSTRACT

Improvement of pedagogical conditions and methodical provision of modern pedagogical technologies to present results based on the theoretical model and increase the creativity of vocational education students. Choosing the theoretical basis for the further formation of methodological activity, finding solutions to the problems of increasing and improving the creative abilities of students of vocational education. Development of exemplary prospective specific plans aimed at improving pedagogical conditions for improving the creativity of students of professional education. Currently, various public events are one of the most widespread forms of social activity and spending free time of the population and satisfy the need of a person to directly enjoy the achievements of political life, sports, culture, creativity, and art.

Key words and concepts: student, motivation, attention, method, education, creativity, ability, development, need.

Enter. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev. "We must satisfy the vital requirements of teachers and coaches, encourage them, ensure that they are satisfied with their work and profession, and it is completely inappropriate to talk about the education of the next generation without solving this issue," Mirziyoev said. We know that the teaching profession is one of the great, honorable, very complex and responsible professions. It is very important to give the right direction to increase the creativity of students. It is very important to give the right direction to increase the creativity of students. As a result of conducting scientific-research work on the issues of students' adaptation to the educational process, the problems of adaptation of students of the 1st stage to higher educational institutions were studied in our country. Since the methodology for solving the above problems has not been created, it is necessary to solve the problems as follows.

It is known that each person has a certain creative power. The basis of this creative power is the creation of new things. Students' imaginations will be creative and creative. In the process of reading educational or fiction literature, students are required to relive the reality described in these books in their memories. Creative imaginations are distinguished from creative imaginations by the independent creation of new patterns. They are reflected in the specific results of the student's activity and depend on the ways of creativity of each person. If creative imagination is manifested in a certain activity, we know that it indicates a high level of development of the student's personality. It is necessary to develop personal imagination. Creative, plot-role games of a cognitive nature are of particular importance in personal development. Because it is the basis for expanding the imagination of students. In the international concept of education defined by UNESCO until 2030, special emphasis is placed on "quality education promotes creative thinking and knowledge, acquires the basics of literacy and numeracy skills, as well as analysis, problem solving, reasoning and other interpersonal and social skills at a high level."

At the current stage of scientific and technical development, the acceleration of production relations, the introduction of new technologies in various aspects of the national economy, and a number of similar factors are causing more physical and mental stress on the human psyche than before. In the work of the teacher, it is necessary to pay attention to the elimination of mental and physical fatigue in students who are mentally or physically tired. This requirement is especially important in the current environment, where the influence of negative psychological factors has increased, and there is a collision with a large amount of information. Pedagogical activity aimed at eliminating mental and physical fatigue in students is "**relaxopedia**" (lat. "relaxation" - weakness, weakening, mental or physical to fall without; pedagogy to eliminate exhaustion) is called. In recent years, this pedagogic opportunity has been widely used in the practice of world education.

Pedagogical relaxation - restoration of students' emotional activity, mental and physical strength and work

Today's widely popular training and self-training in relaxation conditions ensure the creation of a positive environment.

During the relaxation process, students should feel the support of the pedagogue, enjoy his love and sympathy. Only then will a psychological environment be created to eliminate mental stress and physical fatigue in students.

In order to eliminate mental stress and physical fatigue, students should not only learn the basics of relaxation theoretically, but also know how to use them practically.

Communicative influence - in communication with students to be, to match them properly, to them with pedagogic gentleness

As mentioned above, pedagogical delicacy (tact) also has a special place in the work of a skilled pedagogue:

Pedagogical (gentleness) tact is the pedagogue's adherence to existing ethical principles and rules of conduct in communication with students in various forms of

Pedagogical tact is manifested as a form of direct implementation of pedagogical ethics, which is ideologically and practically consistent with the work of a pedagogue. **Tact (diligence)** is a moral behavior, a behavior, which represents the consequence of all objective actions and their subjective acceptance by a person in advance, the manifestation of the search for ways to achieve the set goal more easily. Pedagogical tact is essentially a practical action that requires creative research.

In the article, the professional education students are to be prepared for professional activity by developing their creativity, to become creative, highly qualified professionals in the educational process, to learn, become active, to become an active participant in the educational process, and not to receive ready-made knowledge. , the issue of creating a foundation for the development of a future creative pedagogue is interpreted.

Relevance of the topic. Currently, the legal and normative basis for reforming the system of personnel training and continuous education in educational institutions has been created. The laws "**On Education**" and "**National Program of Personnel Training**" set the task of expanding the scientific outlook, strengthening their creative approach to work, and forming high discipline in the higher education system, which is considered one of the main links of the continuous education system.

The relevance of the topic is determined by the fact that the issues of choosing the theoretical basis for further improvement of methodological activities, increasing the creativity of students of professional education and its development have not yet been resolved. In particular, in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the

development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the priority task of further improving the continuous education system, increasing quality education opportunities, and continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the times of the labor market is defined. Taking this into account, it is urgent to improve the current methodology and teaching-methodical support of professional education students' creativity development based on advanced approaches and to develop the mechanisms of mastery results.

Organization of methodological bases for improving the creativity of students of professional education;

The content and essence of improving students' creativity based on the competence approach.

Problems of pedagogical competence in improving the creative activity of students of professional education.

Features of improving students' creativity in circles based on special subjects based on foreign experiences.

In improving and educating the creativity of students of professional education, it is necessary to form him as an independent thinker, independent learner, able to independently organize his activities, self-control, self-developing, and have his own personal position. Although the concepts of pedagogical creativity and pedagogical skill are close to each other, they do not have the same meaning. The owner of pedagogical skills is a master of his profession at a high level and a person who has gained a lot of experience. And in creativity, it can be a young artist who has just started his work, but he is not yet a master. A creative person can be a creative expert. A creative person can be formed in a higher educational institution and in the environment of a creative team. Being a creative person is related to independent education and creative work. He becomes a person of high level of professionalism during continuous education.

We divide creativity into four levels

- thorough acquisition of knowledge and skills related to one's profession;
- ability to form creative thinking;
- the ability to show creativity;
- inquisitiveness, tendency to research.

A creative person is formed based on the ability to show the above. Formation of our generation of creative students leads to creative and innovative development of education.

The level of study of the problem. A.R. Khodzhaboev, P.Z.Ishanov, D.Fayzullaeva, K.D.Mirsaidov, O'.D.Khidirov, R.K.Choriev, on the problems of the development system of methodological support for the organization of innovative

cooperation in the formation of creativity in the training of students of professional education. It was considered in the research works of Z.K. Ismailova, A. Shoyusupova. Development of innovative cooperation in the preparation of students of the professional education field, increasing their creativity, and coordination of processes V.P.Bespalko, S.D.Dolimov, R.Kh.Zhoraev, L.V.Zankov, D.Zokhidova, I.Ya.Lerner, I.T.Ogorodnikov, N.Saidakhmedov, M.N.Skatkin, Scientific works of O. Tolipov, Ya. Kh. Khaidarov and others are dedicated.

The need to develop a methodology for increasing the efficiency of using modern methods in the development of the creativity of students of professional education became the basis for choosing the topic "**Creating pedagogical conditions for increasing the creativity of students of professional education**".

The purpose. Development of a methodology for increasing the creativity of students of professional education based on modern pedagogical technologies and achieving its effectiveness.

Tasks;

- Creation of innovative cooperation in increasing the creativity of students of professional education, developing an action program after studying all the necessary conditions provided for in the Regulations of the educational institution;
- Creation of prospective recommendations and guidelines for students of professional education in accordance with the curriculum and programs approved by the state education standard;
- Development of exemplary prospective plans aimed at improving the pedagogical conditions for increasing the creativity of students of professional education;

Object The process of improving the pedagogical conditions for increasing the creativity of students of professional education.

Subject. Developments on methodical support for improving pedagogical conditions for increasing creativity of students of professional education.

Scientific news.

- To increase creativity in the training of students of professional education, to organize methodological support for the organization of innovative cooperation, to provide students with educational programs, as well as reforms, existing problems, achievements, advanced techniques and technologies carried out by mature specialists of the academic lyceum and educational institutions under its jurisdiction. as well as developing a plan for organizing lectures and roundtable discussions dedicated to strategic directions;

- Development of an action program to work with professors and teachers who are devoted to their field and conduct research at a high quality level, as well as talented and active students in public affairs, in order to organize innovative cooperation in improving the creativity of their students;

- Development of the activity of the "Master Apprentice System" in the establishment and improvement of the integration of science, education and production in the organization of methodical support for the organization of innovative cooperation in increasing the creativity of students, creation of developments on the comprehensive support of talented students within the framework of scientific and research works;

- Development of a scientific-practical conference program based on the participation of pedagogues and engineer-pedagogues of academic lyceums under the management of higher education, vocational education department and management of innovative new textbooks, training manuals and computer programs to increase students' creativity;

Conclusions and suggestions

Every pedagogue should give high-quality and effective lessons in compliance with modern scientific and technical requirements. We believe that it is useful for pedagogues to organize education using elements of pedagogical technology and innovative interactive educational methods in the lesson, to use the latest pedagogical technologies to increase students' creativity.

improvement of their knowledge and skills in the form of creative research and direct it to a certain goal. In this:

- to form the qualities of creativity in themselves;
- tend to manage the process of creative research;
- should remember that creativity depends on pedagogical, psychological and theoretical preparation of the future student.

Methodological foundations of improving the development of pedagogical and methodical processes in order to organize innovative cooperation in increasing the creativity of students of professional education, as well as creating educational and methodological support for the development of the personal activity of a pedagogue in the system of organizing innovative cooperation in the training of future teachers of vocational education.

Organization of innovative cooperation in the course of classes, increasing the creativity of vocational education students based on the methodology of creating a teaching-methodical process in the system of increasing efficiency and the results of experience. To improve the creativity of students, to guide them in the study of their interests, to develop their creativity, to ensure continuous improvement of their skills.

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